

The unification of Turkic Speaking States in the 21st century and its role in the geopolitical arena

Barchinoy Juraeva Musallamovna, an international journalist, independent researcher at the Department of "Human Rights and Media" under the Uzbek University of Journalism and Mass Communications

Annotation:

This research explores the growing cooperation and integration among Turkic-speaking states in the 21st century. It examines the political, economic, and cultural dimensions of this unification process, with particular focus on the activities of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS). The study analyzes how shared historical roots, linguistic and cultural affinities, and common geopolitical interests are driving these nations closer together. Furthermore, it assesses the geopolitical significance of this unification within Central Asia, the Caucasus, the Middle East, and the broader Eurasian region, as well as its implications for global political dynamics and relations with major world powers.

Keywords:

Turkic-speaking states, Organization of Turkic States, geopolitics, regional integration, political cooperation, economic alliance, cultural ties, Eurasia, international relations.

The emergence of international intergovernmental organizations on the political scene began to acquire a global character in the second half of the 19th century. In the past, the international community did not feel the need for the creation of such platforms. In the 20th century, such platforms began to acquire new significance. In particular, the collapse of the USSR, which was considered a super power, created the basis for the formation of a new geopolitical reality.

The world is changing and we are facing various challenges, problems and crises every day. Unrest in some countries, escalation of wars, global food and energy crisis and its impact on the entire world economy, rising inflationary pressures, weakening of the world and national economies, impoverishment of millions of people, increasing tensions between the US and China and polarization in Asian countries indicate that the international system is failing. Moreover, the Covid-19 pandemic has exacerbated the economic downturn. We can say that, the world order established after World War II could no longer support the current international system of relations [1]. In the context of fundamental changes in the global socio-political system, the question of how this key Asian region will develop, who or what will influence its future prospects, what should be the political views and social activity of the peoples of the Turkic speaking states, who have a shared history, has become an important strategic task. From this point of view, the establishment of an official organization that would define relations between countries on the basis of mutual cooperation and solidarity was an urgent task.

After the collapse of the Soviet system, the Central Asian countries and Azerbaijan declared their sovereignty and became a full-fledged subject of international relations. In order not to exist in the shadow of hegemonic states or to become dependent on another strong power under the influence of foreign ideology, each country began to independently determine its own path of development and strive to win its place in the international arena [1]. At the same time, the world felt the need for a strong "Turkic geopolitics" to ensure the stable provision of large-scale economic relations among the European and Asian countries and to prevent the Eurasian region from turning into an arena of rivalry for super powers.

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All these factors brought forward the idea of unifying the Turkic states. In fact, there is nothing new in the promotion of this ideology. It is historically well known that our great ancestor Amir Temur also had a dream of a unified Turan that would bring together the Turkic speaking nations. Turkey has taken on this responsibility. Some CA countries, Turkey and Azerbaijan became the full fledged members of the organization. Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan did not join the organization and declared a status of "positive neutrality". However, these two countries were considered important for the new organization. This is due to the fact that half of the Turkic-speaking population of the Central Asian countries live in Uzbekistan, and Turkmenistan ranks 4th in the world in terms of proven gas reserves [1].

However, due to the fact that this political platform was not well systematized, as well as due to the lack of financial support for the initiatives put forward, and also due to the fact that the Muslim countries of the region selected the way of development on secular principles, Turkey's participation in the formation of new Turkic-speaking countries in the period from 1991 to 1996 was reduced. Only by 1996, this organization became a structured entity equipped with real political tools and long-term aims, and later, as evidence of this, the Council of Turkic-Speaking States was created.

On October 30, 1992, Turkey initiated the first "Summit of Turkic-Speaking States" was held in Ankara. State leaders of Azerbaijan, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan became honorary participants of this summit. Subsequent summits of the presidents took place in Istanbul in 1994, 2001 and 2010, in Bishkek in 1995, in Tashkent in 1996, in Astana in 1998, in Baku in 2000 and in Antalya in 2006.

The summit held on October 3, 2009 opened a new century for the Turkic countries in the true sense. It was at this summit that the "Nakhichevan Agreement on the Establishment of the Cooperation Council of Turkic-Speaking States" was signed between Turkey, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, and Kyrgyzstan, and as a result, the Cooperation Council of Turkic-Speaking States (Turkic Council) was established. However, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan kept neutral position in this process. The key goal of this intergovernmental organization was to develop comprehensive cooperation between the Turkic states. Thus, the 2009 Nakhchivan summit became a historic step that institutionalized relations between the Turkic states. The uniqueness of the organization is that it covers various areas of cooperation. In particular, according to Article 2 of the Nakhchivan Agreement, the key goals and objectives of the organization include issues of strengthening and maintaining peace and security, as well as developing effective regional and bilateral cooperation in the political, trade and economic, law enforcement, environmental, cultural, scientific and technical, military and technical, educational, energy, transport and loan services areas [2]. At the same time, the main goals of this document were to strengthen political, economic, cultural, environmental and scientific cooperation, as well as to establish close interaction in areas such as education, transport and finance. However, due to the lack of interest on the part of member states in such sincere efforts, a solid intellectual basis for activating these goals and the lack of consensus at that time, most of these projects remained ink on paper [3].

At the VII summit held in Baku in October 2019, Uzbekistan joined the Council of Turkic Speaking States as a full-fledged member. New era of reforms in the country, the position of the "New Uzbekistan", openness to multilateral platforms in international relations were the main factors for such decision. President Sh. Mirziyoyev initiated the idea that "an open and constructive foreign policy meets, first and foremost, national interests." After joining the organization, Uzbekistan

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quickly became its most active member. At the same time, the Council entered a period of intensified cooperation among the Turkic states.

The analysis of the integration process of the Turkic states can be divided into three periods. In the first stage, the Turkic states established cooperation in the cultural and educational sphere (1992–2008). In order to achieve effective results from the goals set, the Turkic Agency for Cooperation and Development (TIKA) was established in 1992. TIKA's coordinating offices began operating in Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan. One of the organization's largest projects, "Turkology," was largely implemented in 21 countries around the world. It envisaged the establishment of departments for the study of history of the Turkic speaking nations and culture in various universities [3].

In 1993, the International Organization of Turkic Culture (TURKSOY) was founded, and currently it's activity aimed to strengthen the cultural and humanitarian relations of the Turkic speaking countries, and to promote the culture of Turkic nations at a high level on a global scale.

The second stage of political integration of the Turkic states continued between 2008 and 2020. In November 2008, the Parliamentary Assembly of the Turkic speaking States (TurkPA) was established. [4].

As mentioned above, the Turkic Council was established on October 3, 2009, and in 2010, the Turkic Academy was opened in the capital of Kazakhstan, Astana. In 2014, it acquired the status of an international organization and currently it's key role is to bring together the academic communities of Turkic speaking countries and popularize the intellectual potential of Turkic speaking countries in the world. [5].

At the summit held on November 11, 2021, the Turkic Council was renamed to the Organization of Turkic speaking States.

Turkmenistan has been granted an observer status in the Organization of Turkic States. At the meeting, after announcing the renaming the title of the organization, Turkish President Recep Tayyip Erdogan made an important proposal, where he stated that, "From now on, we will firmly spread our roots, grow, develop and progress faster than we have done so far." [6]

Turkish Foreign Minister Mavlud Cavusoglu described the Turkic Council as a "meeting of family members" and explained the reason of renaming the organization's title saying that: "This achievement belongs to all of us. To adapt to a changing world, we are now on the verge of a significant transformation processes. We are the kings of a huge tree drinking water from the same root. Relying on our roots, we have to strengthen our unity and also increase our power on the world stage"[6].

Thus, since 2021, the third stage of integration of the Turkic speaking states has been launched, the geography of the organization's activity has expanded, and cooperation between the member states has intensified.

More than ten documents, including the "Turkic World Vision - 2040" program were signed at the historic summit held in Istanbul in November 2021. The Charter on the Partners of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) was also approved during the summit. Good-neighborly relations, harmony and the use of the potential of cooperation in the spirit of striving for progress through equality, trust, mutual benefit, mutual consultation and cooperation have become the main goals of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS). That is, this document envisaged uniting all Turkic-speaking nations into a single super-confederation through the concept of "Great Turan." He also

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stated that the new structure is open to establishing constructive cooperation relations with third countries and international organizations.

In an article published in the Anadolu Publishing Agency, Turkish professor Cengiz Tomar emphasizes the need for the the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) to develop a roadmap for implementing critical solutions, where he writes: “With the implementation of the programmatic provisions of the “Turkic World Vision 2040” adopted at the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) Summit held in Istanbul on November 12, 2021, the organization will gain flesh and blood”. The document, which aims to create a prosperous Turkic world, places special emphasis on concepts such as democracy, economic and social reforms, transparency and anti-corruption, as well as gender equality to achieve these goals. The document provides for cooperation in such areas as economics, healthcare, transport, education, energy, as well as the creation of advisory mechanisms on international and regional foreign policy issues. The document also includes articles on combating radicalisation, extremism, Islamophobia, border security, drug trafficking, illegal migration, trafficking in human beings and weapons, organised crime, financial and cybercrime, migration management and security cooperation.” [7]

As professor states, the potential of the Turkic states, which have a rich historical and cultural heritage, can be supported through joint tourism and the Great Silk Road projects, turning it into one of the main driving forces of the organization from an economic point of view. He also noted that the areas of transportation and customs currently are the most painful subjects among the Turkic states, and that the “Turkic World Vision 2040” opens up practical opportunities in this regard, in particular by eliminating the existing economic barriers along the East-West corridor through the Caspian Sea.

The Samarkand Summit in 2022, as expressed by the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, marked the beginning of a new stage of growth in the modern history of the civilization of the Turkic world.

At the summit of the heads of state members of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS), Sh. Mirziyoyev put forward a number of following important proposals: “While getting prepared to the Summit, we have thoroughly analyzed the activities of our Organization. The mutual trade between our countries constitutes only 4% of total foreign trade. And the rest of it corresponds to the share of third countries. In addition, some import customs tariffs between our countries remain high. In order to fundamentally change the situation in this strategic direction, to ensure free movement of trade, investment and services, we put forward the initiative on establishment of a «space of new economic opportunities» within our Organization. To implement this plan, I propose to hold an annual International Turkic Economic Forum involving the member and observer states of our Organization as well as leading world business representatives. Another urgent issue of strategic importance on the agenda is the strengthening the transport connectivity. For instance, we are speaking a lot about the transcaspian international corridor, but we have to accomplish a lot to achieve tangible results. We should focus on increasing the competitiveness of transit corridors in our region; introducing the most favorable tariffs for business; creating a modern transport infrastructure. In this regard, we call on the states of our Organization to join the system of electronic transport permits exchange recently introduced between Türkiye and Uzbekistan.” [8]

President Mirziyoyev also proposed to carry out institutional reforms within the Organization, emphasizing that much work remains to be done to systematically coordinate the tasks facing the Organization and ensure their effectiveness, as well as to combine joint efforts so that in the future

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the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) can function on the basis of a completely new, effective system.

A number of experts also noted that this summit had a significant role in the history of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS): “First of all, we have to note that the Samarkand Summit, where the crucial issues were discussed and important documents were signed, was of great importance for the expansion of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) and the integration of the Turkic world. Another important event for the prospects of trade and economic cooperation was the official creation of the Turkic Investment Fund within the framework of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) at the summit in Samarkand. The Samarkand Declaration considered the adoption of the Strategy for the Facilitation of Trade Procedures between Member States, as well as decisions to complete negotiations on the Agreement on Cooperation in the field of the Digital Economy and the Agreement on Free Trade in Services and Investments, Trade and Customs Procedures. “In the near future, work on simplification and harmonization within the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) framework will accelerate,” writes Omirbek Khanayi, a research fellow at the Eurasian Research Institute at the Khoja Akhmed Yassawi International Turkic-Kazakh University [9].

At the same summit, the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus was admitted to the organization as an observer member state. This event was greeted by the public with great enthusiasm.

It is worth noting that over the past short period of time, Uzbekistan has established mutually beneficial and large-scale cooperation in more than 30 important areas. A number of initiatives are being put forward to further improve the future activities of the organization.

In particular, Sh. Miziyoyev proposed to work out a short and medium term strategy for economic cooperation of member countries, taking into account the pandemic and post pandemic period, based on the conceptual document “Vision of the Turkic World – 2040”. He stressed the need to focus on eliminating the negative consequences of the ongoing global crisis, restoring trade, investment, industrial and transportation communications, and making full use of the opportunities for business and interregional cooperation in the new conditions through the widespread introduction of e-commerce and digital technologies.

In recent years, the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) has not only become a platform for peace and cooperation of interregional and global significance, but has also become one of the centers of economic growth in the world. These changes are also due to the political and economic position of Uzbekistan in this structure.

In part, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his speech at Council of Heads of States within the framework of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) held in Kazakhstan in November 2023, positively assessed the economic potential of the countries, where he stressed that "The Organization of Turkic speaking States increasingly holds a unique and important position in the new world order and system of international institutions that is being formed today. The scope of activity of our Organization, covering a population of 160 million people, is also an area of great economic opportunities.

In the near future the Turkic Investment Bank will start its work. In order to strengthen industrial cooperation among our countries and implement large investment projects, the next stage should also intensify the initiatives on the establishment of the Turkic Development Bank... We need to jointly implement specific measures aimed at eliminating trade barriers, the widespread introduction of new mechanisms for increasing export and import volumes, and the development of electronic trading platforms”[10].

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The active integration of the Turkic states can also be seen in the acceptance of Turkmenistan, which kept neutrality for many years, as an “observer state” in 2022. Turkmenistan plays an important role in the implementation of projects related to transit between Europe and Asia and access to world markets, as well as in connecting the “ties” of the Turkic states of Europe and Asia. These projects can be implemented without Turkmenistan, but the most promising routes in Central Asia get across this country. In particular, we note the efficiency of the newly built port, or rather, the shortest route in the entire Middle East (taking into account Afghanistan) passes through it [11].

Another important event was the creation of the Turkic Investment Fund at the extraordinary summit of the Organization of Turkic States in Ankara on March 16, 2023. In turn, in November 2023, Uzbekistan adopted and ratified the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Ratification of the Agreement on the Establishment of the Turkic Investment Fund (Ankara, March 16, 2023)” [12].

In the near future, it is planned to further increase the joint investment fund with an initial capital of 500 million US dollars and reach the indicators up to 1 billion US dollars. This fund creates important opportunities for business circles to establish effective cooperation and strengthen small and medium businesses [13].

In recent years, the creation of a unified information space of the Turkic countries has become one of the main tasks of the Organization. The development of digital technologies in the modern world has led to an unprecedented increase in the influence of the media, especially social networks, on the formation of public opinion and consciousness. In this sense, the effective use of media platforms of the organization’s member states in covering the goals and activities of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS), the development of cooperation in the field of media and communications between Turkic-speaking states, and the implementation of joint projects are of great importance. In particular, at the 3rd meeting of ministers, high-ranking officials responsible for information and media held in Baku in 2022, the parties approved the “Action Program for 2021-2022” and agreed to establish a Coordination Committee for information and media in cooperation with the information and media agencies of Turkic-speaking countries [3].

At the 1st meeting of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) Member States on Audiovisual Media held in Baku in October 2022, Elmira Valizoda, Head of the Digital Media Sector of the Presidential Administration of Azerbaijan, emphasized that the development of bilateral and multilateral cooperation among the public mass media agencies within the framework of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) is the imperative demands of our time. Valizoda noted that in the era of digital media, copyright protection and the production of quality programs make a significant contribution to the development of countries [14].

The Turkic Council Social Media Education Program was organized by the Communications Directorate of the Turkish Presidential Administration to share knowledge and experience in the field of social media and countering disinformation among the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) Member States. The Media Forum of the Turkic Council became another important event. The forum, organized under the motto “Common Past, Strong Future,” was attended by representatives of leading media organizations from the member states of Turkey, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, as well as observer states Hungary, Turkmenistan and Northern Cyprus. Issues such as possible cooperation in the field of media, television shows and cinematography in the Turkic world, as well as issues of the development of social networks and the joint fight against disinformation were discussed at the forum [15].

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At present, in addition to the integration of the Turkic states, the “integration of Greater Eurasia” is important for the whole of Eurasia. This can be considered in a continental, global and regional context. This scheme logically suggests cooperation between the EAEU, the Arab world, and the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) within the framework of its "One Belt, One Road" geoeconomic megaproject. Speaking about the development prospects of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS), it should be noted that the organization has enormous potential. The most important aspect of the issue is how to use this potential to achieve the strategic goals outlined in the Turkic World Vision 2040 concept adopted at the 2021 Istanbul Summit. Against the backdrop of geopolitical processes, great prospects are opening up for the Turkic states, including cooperation in the energy sector. Such major energy projects as the Baku-Tbilisi-Chaykhun oil pipeline and the Trans-Anatolian gas pipeline (TANAP) are already under implementation. In addition, cooperation in the field of transport and logistics is of great importance, which will contribute to further increasing the efficiency of the “Middle Corridor”[16].

However, there are also contradictory opinions about the future of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS). For example, Chinese scientist Zhang Yuyan claims in his research work that the prospects of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) are limited due to a number of objective and subjective reasons. In his scientific work, he enumerates a number of factors that hinder the sustainable development of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS). For example, the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) members lack motivation to participate in the activities of the Organization, which hinders its development; the activity area of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) does not have an integral geographical zone, which is one of the objective obstacles complicating the process of Turkic integration; the diversity of geopolitical and geoeconomic interests of member and observer countries weakens the effectiveness of their collective actions; the efforts of new independent states to create titular nations are somewhat at odds with the goals of Turkic integration; Experience shows that attempts to integrate the CIS countries over the past 30 years have failed, and the desire to integrate the CIS into a wider space is a long-term process; Turkic integration lacks a strong leader. Turkey's economic situation is barely capable of supporting the entire Turkic world, and its cultural appeal is not considered a sufficient force to dominate the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) [1].

Contrary to this opinion, it can be said that in recent years the activity geography of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) has expanded, covering strategically important regions. The organization also acts as a qualitatively new model of regional cooperation with great potential and all the conditions for establishing sustainable integration in Eurasia. Today, the integration of the Turkic states is institutionalized and they have a clear development strategy in which economic cooperation is a priority. Currently, the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) is an organization of member states under one roof that strengthens large-scale cooperation relations.

As the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) strengthens its position on the world stage, it is also becoming one of the leading forces in the integration processes in Eurasia. In recent years, cooperation among the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) countries has become more pragmatic and meaningful. If at the initial stages great importance was attached to the activation of cultural and humanitarian ties, today the issues of strengthening trade, economic and investment ties and the development of transcontinental transit corridors have come to the fore [17].

The Turkic countries have enormous economic and social potential. Today, the territory of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) is about 4.2 million square meters, the population is 170 million people. Mutual trade value among the countries of the Organization of Turkic Speaking States

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increased by 27% in 2023. Such high growth rates were observed in 2024 as well. This makes the Turkic countries the 13th largest economic group in the world.

Documents that accelerate the integration of the Organization of Turkic Speaking States countries, such as the "Vision of the Turkic World 2040" and roadmaps such as the Strategy of the Organization of Turkic States for 2022-2026, show that the Turkic world has great potential for joint action and these factors can help the organization to hold a strong leadership position in the world arena. Therefore, the task of the organization's member states is to protect the the Organization of Turkic Speaking States from possible negative factors, both internal and external, to make efforts to broaden its activities and to help the organization to fulfill its historical mission.

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